

The Effectiveness of a Differentiated Learning Model Based on Identification, Reflection and Improvement to Improve the Reading Ability of Early Grade Students in Elementary School

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the effectiveness of a differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement to improve the reading ability of early grade students in elementary school. Using a quasi-experimental design involving 5 elementary schools. The findings of the study showed that there was a significant difference in the improvement of reading ability of early grade students between the experimental class and the control class. The differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement has high effectiveness in improving the reading ability of early grade students. This means that the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement has a positive impact and allows teachers to identify student needs at the beginning of learning, then teachers reflect on the learning process and results carried out, then make improvements (improve) to the learning strategy, especially adjusted to the student's learning readiness. The results of this study reveal that the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement is effective in improving the reading ability of early grade students, so that it can be a solution to overcome the difficulty or low ability of students in reading and recommends to develop a more effective and innovative learning model in the early grade.

KEYWORDS: Differentiated Learning, Effectiveness, Identification-based, Reflection and Improvement, Reading.

INTRODUCTION

Reading ability is an important foundation in the learning process at all levels of education and must be mastered by students [1]. Through reading, students not only gain new information or knowledge and insights, but also develop critical thinking skills, imagination and understanding of the world around them [2]. Reading ability will affect the learning process and outcomes [3]. Good reading skills will greatly support students' success in learning all subjects and adapting to an increasingly complex learning environment [4].

Improving the reading ability of early grade students is often a challenge for teachers [5]. Various factors such as differences in learning styles, the level of comprehension and students' interest in reading are obstacles that need to be overcome [6]. Learning that is one-way and does not accommodate the diversity of students can create difficulties and make students lack motivation to learn and interest in reading [7].

As an effort to overcome these challenges, the differentiated learning model can be used as one of the effective solutions [8], [9]. Differentiated learning is an approach and learning model that recognizes that students have unique characteristics, so it requires learning that is tailored to their needs, interests and learning styles [10]. In the context of reading learning, this model teachers design learning with various variations that are in accordance with the level of student learning readiness [11], [12].

To improve the reading ability of early grade students who are still low, it is very necessary to make efforts from teachers and related parties in designing learning according to the needs of students [13]. Differentiated learning has been shown to meet the needs of diverse students, and can significantly improve individual learning [14]. Teachers adapt learning in the classroom and make a positive contribution [15], becoming a complex classroom management solution [16].

The implementation of a differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement plays a very important role [17]. Through identification, teachers can identify the strengths and weaknesses of each student in reading. Through reflection, teachers can analyze learning outcomes and identify areas that need improvement. Then through improvement, teachers can make adjustments to the learning approach that has been implemented previously so that it is more effective in improving students' reading skills [18]. Some research results show that the reading ability of early grade students is still low, students have difficulty reading [19].

In line with these problems, a differentiated learning model was found as a solution by referring to the results of research that showed the effectiveness of differentiated learning in improving various aspects of learning, there was a positive impact [20], there was a learning adjustment so that students could understand it more easily [21], modifying learning according to student needs so that learning was active [22], changing learning strategies to use the style that best suits students [23].

This study specifically examines the effectiveness of differentiated learning models based on identification, reflection and improvement to improve the reading ability of early grade students in elementary school. Therefore, this study was conducted to answer the research question, namely "How effective is the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement to improve the reading ability of early grade students in elementary school?"

METHOD

This study designs and evaluates the implementation of a differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement to improve the reading ability of early grade students in elementary school. This study uses a quantitative approach with a quasi-experimental design, the researcher compares the experimental group (which implements a differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement) with the control group (conventional learning) without full randomization of the group. This research was conducted in Majene district at SDN 2 Kampung Baru, SDN 4 Tanjung Batu, SDN 6 Kampung Baru, SDN 1 Luaor and SDN 28 Luaor. Each school has one experimental class and one control class, especially in class II with the consideration that in this class students should ideally be able to read.

The experimental class was given treatment by implementing an IRB-based differentiated learning model to improve reading ability, while the control class was not given treatment, learning took place conventionally. The IRB-based differentiated learning model used in this study is the result of the development of an IRB-based differentiated learning model.

To obtain data on effectiveness, an assessment of reading ability was carried out to students. The instrument used to obtain effectiveness data is a reading ability test given to students in the form of an initial test (pretest) and a final test (posttest) in the learning process in the classroom. Pretest and posttest use the same instrument. The test results measure reading ability which is categorized into several levels, starting from letter recognition, syllable recognition, word recognition, reading simple sentences and reading and comprehension of texts.

The analysis of the reading effectiveness of early grade students in elementary school was carried out using the Mann-Whitney test and the N-gain Score test. Furthermore, the results of the N-gain score ($\langle g \rangle$) are converted into the following categorizations:

Table 1. Categories Effectiveness

No.	(N-gain) or ($\langle g \rangle$)	Effectiveness Level
1	$\langle g \rangle > 0,7$	Tall
2	$0,3 \leq \langle g \rangle \leq 0,7$	Keep
3	$\langle g \rangle > 0,3$	Low

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effectiveness test of the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement was carried out by looking at the impact of learning on the improvement of reading ability of early grade students in elementary school. Data for the effectiveness test were collected through the reading ability assessment of early grade students who followed the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement (experimental class) and students who participated in conventional learning (control class). The results of the reading ability test for early grade students in elementary school in the experimental class of 125 students are described in the following figure.

Figure 1. Percentage of Reading Ability of Early Elementary School Students In the Experimental Class

Based on the data in Figure 1, the pretest results showed that the reading ability of 5.60% of the students in the experimental class was at the stage of letter recognition, 9.60% was at the stage of syllable recognition, 26.40% was at the stage of word recognition, 50.40% was at the stage of being able to read simple sentences and 8.00% was at the stage of being able to read and understand texts. Then the posttest results showed that the reading ability of 5.60% of the experimental class students was at the stage of word recognition, 20.00% was at the stage of being able to read simple sentences and 74.40% was at the stage of being able to read and understand texts. This means that there is an improvement in the reading ability of early grade students in elementary school after the implementation of the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement. Where before the intervention was carried out on the implementation of the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement, most of the reading ability of early grade students was at the stage of being able to read simple sentences by 50.40%. However, after the intervention, the reading ability of most of the students in the experimental class was at the stage of being able to read and understand the text by 74.40%.

Students in the experimental class before being given the intervention of the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and correction as many as 8% of students who were able to read and understand the text became 74.4% after the intervention was carried out, there was an increase in the number of students who were able to read 66.4%. This indicates that the differentiated learning model has a positive impact on improving the reading ability of early grade students.

Furthermore, the results of the reading ability test of 122 students in the early grades in elementary school are described in the following figure.

Figure 2. Percentage of Reading Ability of Early Elementary School Students In the Control Class

Based on the data in figure 2, the results of the pretest in the control class showed that the reading ability of grade students was 15.57% at the stage of syllable recognition, 25.41% at the stage of word recognition, 37.70% at the stage of being able to read simple sentences and 21.31% at the stage of being able to read and understand texts. Then the results of the posttest reading ability of control class students 5.74% were at the stage of syllable recognition, 18.85% were at the stage of word recognition, 45.90% were at the stage of being able to read simple sentences and 29.51% were at the stage of being able to read and understand texts. This means that there is not much improvement in the reading ability of early grade students in elementary school, after the implementation of differentiated learning based on identification, reflection and improvement. Where before the intervention was carried out in the implementation of the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement as the reading ability of early grade students was at the stage of being able to read simple sentences by 37.70%. Then after the intervention, the reading ability of the control class students mostly remained at the stage of being able to read simple sentences by 45.90%. Students in the control class with pretest results as many as 21.31% of students who were able to read and understand the text became the results of the posttest 29.51%, an increase in the number of students who were able to read 8.2%. When compared to the experimental class, it shows that the experimental class has a more positive impact, where in the experimental class there is an increase in reading and comprehension skills of 64.4% while in the control class there is an increase of 8.2%. This indicates that the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement has a positive impact on improving the reading ability of early grade students in elementary school.

To reveal the effectiveness of the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement on the improvement of reading ability of early grade students in elementary school, it was statistically tested. Before the data on the results of the reading ability test of early grade students in the experimental class and control class were tested for effectiveness, a normality test and a homogeneity test were first carried out.

The results of the normality test data of the reading ability test results of students in the experimental class and the control class showed that the data was not distributed normally. Meanwhile, the results of the data homogeneity test showed that the reading ability test results of the experimental class and the control class students showed that the data variance was heterogeneous (not the same). Furthermore, the effectiveness test uses non-parametric statistical analysis using the Mann-Whitney test and the N-Gain Score test.

The results of the Mann-Whitney test, the U value is calculated $0.000 < 0.05$. This indicates that there is a significant difference in the improvement of reading ability of early grade students between the experimental class and the control class. This difference shows that the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and correction has a positive impact on the improvement of reading ability of early grade students. Where the learning applied in the experimental class has a greater impact than the learning in the control class.

The results of the N-gain Score test obtained a value of $<g>$ of 0.867 in the experimental class, in the category of $(<g>) > 0.7$. This shows that the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and correction has high effectiveness in improving the reading ability of early grade students. This improvement can be interpreted as students experiencing significant progress in reading ability after the implementation of the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement. Thus, these results provide strong evidence to support the use of differentiated learning models based on identification, reflection and improvement in improving the reading ability of early grade students in elementary school.

The results of this study are in line with some previous research results that reveal that differentiated learning improves reading comprehension ability [24]. improving reading performance [25]. Differentiated learning through content in the media and teaching materials that are tailored to students' learning readiness shows inclusive learning that has a positive impact [26].

This study shows that this differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement has a significant impact on the reading ability of early grade students. This learning model allows teachers to identify student needs at the beginning of learning, then teachers reflect on the learning process and results carried out, and then make improvements (improve) to learning strategies.

The identification stage in differentiated learning based on identification, reflection and correction allows teachers to understand students' initial ability to read. Through formative assessments, teachers can identify the strengths and weaknesses of each student. Information is an important basis in designing relevant learning and adjusting to student learning readiness. By understanding the needs of students, teachers provide appropriate and effective learning to achieve maximum reading ability.

The reflection stage in differentiated learning based on identification, reflection and correction encourages students to reflect on the learning process. Through reflection activities, students are invited to evaluate and realize the reading skills that have been achieved, identify the difficulties they face, and formulate strategies to overcome these difficulties. Reflection helps students develop awareness to be more independent and responsible in learning, and is able to improve directed reading skills.

The improvement stage in the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement is a follow-up to the identification and reflection process. Based on the results of identification and reflection, teachers and students together make specific and measurable improvements. This plan can be in the form of selecting more effective learning strategies, using appropriate learning resources, or providing additional support for students in need. This repair process is cyclical, where after improvements are made, students return to reflect to evaluate the effectiveness of the improvements that have been made. Thus, the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement becomes a continuous and adaptive process, which is always adjusted to the needs and development of students.

This study has shown that the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and correction gives significant results in improving the reading ability of early grade students in elementary school. Students who learn with this model show better improvement compared to students who learn with the conventional model. Teachers conduct initial assessments to find out the level of students' reading ability, for example by asking students to read short texts and answer questions related to comprehension. Teachers reflect on the results of the assessment to group students based on their reading ability level. Teachers also record the interests and learning styles of each student. Teachers design differentiated learning. For example, for students who still have trouble spelling, teachers provide simple letter cards and words. For students who are already fluent in reading, teachers provide more complex and challenging texts. Teachers also use a variety of learning methods, such as group discussions, role plays, or using interesting learning media.

However, there are also research results that show that there are factors that hinder teachers in implementing differentiated learning models in the classroom, including; school administration/leadership, various diversity in the classroom, availability of lesson package books that have a large stock [27], lack of appropriate resources and limited devices to suit the needs of students [28].

Paying attention to the results of this study, the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement can be recommended as one of the effective learning to improve the reading ability of early grade students in elementary school [29]. Teachers need to understand and deepen the characteristics and learning needs of students and design learning that has an impact according to these needs [30]. In addition, teachers need to create a positive learning environment [31], so that students feel comfortable and motivated to learn.

An effective learning model must be able to accommodate these differences in learning styles, so that all students can learn optimally [27]. An effective learning model must be able to provide flexibility to teachers to adapt learning methods and materials to the needs of each student [31].

The differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement has high effectiveness. This is in line with the opinion that differentiated learning significantly improves student learning outcomes [32]. This model is effective because it adapts the content, process, and learning products to the needs, interests, and learning styles of each student [33]. Differentiated learning helps teachers to respond to individual student differences in learning readiness, interests, and learning profiles [34]. This model allows students to learn at a level that suits their abilities, thereby minimizing frustration and increasing motivation [35]. Differentiated learning helps reduce the gap between students with different abilities, thus providing equal opportunities for success [36]. This model increases student engagement because the materials and tasks provided are relevant and interesting [37], and encourages students to learn actively and independently, thereby increasing comprehension [38].

Thus, differentiated learning is a flexible and adaptive model, which can be applied in various subjects and grade levels [39]. This model can be integrated with various other learning strategies that accommodate student activity [40]. This shows that differentiated learning based on identification, reflection and correction has high effectiveness in improving the reading ability of early grade students in elementary school. This model is an effective approach to improve student learning outcomes, meet individual needs, create an inclusive environment, increase student engagement, and be flexible and adaptive in efforts to improve reading skills. Thus, this model is highly recommended untuk diterapkan dalam praktik pembelajaran di kelas awal sekolah dasar.

CONCLUSION

The differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and improvement has high effectiveness in improving the reading ability of early grade students in elementary school. Where the reading ability of early grade students has significantly improved in the class that carries out differentiated learning compared to conventional learning. This implies that the differentiated learning model based on identification, reflection and correction not only improves reading ability, but also provides better results than conventional learning.

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REFERENCES

1. Suson, R., Baratbata, C., Anos, W., Ermac, E., Aranas, A. G., Malabago, N., Galamiton, N., & Capuyan, D, "Differentiated instruction for basic reading comprehension in Philippine settings", *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(9), 3814–3824, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.080904>.
2. Annela, A., & Safran, S, "Analysis of Early Reading Difficulties for Elementary School Students." *Scaffolding: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam Dan Multikulturalisme*, 5(2), 466–484, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.37680/scaffolding.v5i2.3121>.
3. Damaianti, V. S., Rahma, R., & Astini, M. P, "Basic Dimensions of Early Reading Skills of Elementary School Students in Bandung", *Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*, 26(1), 39, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.17977/um048v26i1p39-46>.
4. Umah, E. C., & Hariyanto, *Improving Students' Reading Ability in Elementary Schools Through the Reading Clinic Program* (pp. 106–122), 2023, https://doi.org/10.2991/978-2-38476-038-1_13.
5. Hapsari, E. D., Rizaldy, D. R., Eko, K., Setiawan, P., & Herawati, "Analysis of Beginning Reading Ability in Lower Grade Elementary School Students", *Journal of Language and Education Studies Lingeduca: Journal of Language and Education Studies*, 3(3), 2024, <https://doi.org/10.70177/lingeduca.v3i3.1297>.
6. Tomlinson, C. A. , *The differentiated classroom : responding to the needs of all learners*. Pearson Education, 2005.
7. Smets, W., & Struyven, K, "A teachers' professional development programme to implement differentiated instruction in secondary education: How far do teachers reach?", *Cogent Education*, 7(1), 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2020.1742273>.
8. Melesse, T., & Belay, S, "Differentiating instruction in primary and middle schools: Does variation in students' learning attributes matter?" *Cogent Education*, 9(1), 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2022.2105552>.
9. Magableh, I. S. I., & Abdullah, A, "The effectiveness of differentiated instruction by streaming: A preliminary study of current practices in the UAE", *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 19(6), 95–110, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.6.6>.
10. Dorfberger, S., & Eyal, M, "The perception and attitude of educators regarding differentiated teaching in elementary and junior high schools", *Social Sciences and Humanities Open*, 8(1), 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2023.100586>.
11. Kahmann, R., Droop, M., & Lazonder, A. W., "Meta-analysis of professional development programs in differentiated instruction", *International Journal of Educational Research*, 116, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2022.102072>.
12. Pozas, M., Letzel, V., & Schneider, C., "Teachers and differentiated instruction: exploring differentiation practices to address student diversity", *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 20(3), 217–230, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1471-3802.12481>.
13. Sumarmi, S. A., & Nur Amalia, "Reading and Viewing Ability of Third Grade Students in Elementary School", *International Journal of Elementary Education*, 7(2), 263–272, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.23887/ijee.v7i2.58628>.

14. Brevik, L. M., Gunnulfsen, A. E., & Renzulli, J. S., "Student teachers' practice and experience with differentiated instruction for students with higher learning potential", *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 71, 34–45, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.12.003>.
15. Gaitas, S., & Alves Martins, M., "Teacher perceived difficulty in implementing differentiated instructional strategies in primary school", *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 21(5), 544–556, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2016.1223180>.
16. Gheysens, E., Consuegra, E., Engels, N., & Struyven, K., "Good Things Come to Those Who Wait: The Importance of Professional Development for the Implementation of Differentiated Instruction", *Frontiers in Education*, 5, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2020.00096>.
17. Smale-Jacobse, A. E., Meijer, A., Helms-Lorenz, M., & Maulana, R., "Differentiated Instruction in Secondary Education: A Systematic Review of Research Evidence", In *Frontiers in Psychology* (Vol. 10), 2019, Frontiers Media S.A. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02366>.
18. D'Intino, J. S., & Wang, L., "Differentiated instruction: A review of teacher education practices for Canadian pre-service elementary school teachers", *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 47(5), 668–681, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2021.1951603>.
19. Eysink, T. H., Hulsbeek, M., & Gijlers, H., "Supporting primary school teachers in differentiating in the regular classroom", *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 66, 107–116, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.04.002>.
20. Frerejean, J., van Geel, M., Keuning, T., Dolmans, D., van Merriënboer, J. J. G., & Visscher, A. J., "Ten steps to 4C/ID: Training differentiation skills in a professional development program for teachers", *Instructional Science*, 49(3), 395–418., 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11251-021-09540-x>]
21. Graham, L. J., Bruin, K. De, Lassig, C., & Spandagou, I., "A scoping review of 20 years of research on differentiation : Investigating conceptualisation , characteristics , and methods used", *The Review of Education*, 9(1), 161–198, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1002/rev3.3238>.
22. Griful-Freixenet, J., Vantieghem, W., Gheysens, E., & Struyven, K., "Connecting beliefs, noticing and differentiated teaching practices: A study among pre-service teachers and teachers", *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 1–18. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2020.1862404>.
23. Jager, L., Denessen, E., Cillessen, A., & Meijer, P. C., "Capturing instructional differentiation in educational research: Investigating opportunities and challenges. *Educational Research*, 64(2), 1–18, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2022.2063751>.
24. Scarparolo, G., & Subban, P., "A systematic review of pre-service teachers' self-efficacy beliefs for differentiated instruction", *Teachers and Teaching*, 27(8), 753–766, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2021.2007371>.
25. Smets, W., & Struyven, K., "Aligning with complexity: System-theoretical principles for research on differentiated instruction", *Frontline Learning Research*, 6(2), 66–80, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.14786/flr.v6i2.340>.
26. Valiandes, S., & Neophytou, L. "Teachers' professional development for differentiated instruction in mixed-ability classrooms: Investigating the impact of a development program on teachers' professional learning and on students' achievement", *Teacher Development*, 22(1), 123–138, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13664530.2017.1338196>.
27. Van Geel, M., Keuning, T., & Safar, I., "How teachers develop skills for implementing differentiated instruction: Helpful and hindering factors. *Teaching and Teacher Education: Leadership and Professional Development*, 1, 1–11, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tatelp.2022.100007>.
28. Yuen, M., Chan, S., Chan, C., Fung, D. C., Cheung, W. M., Kwan, T., & Leung, F. K., "Differentiation in key learning areas for gifted students in regular classes: A project for primary school teachers in Hong Kong", *Gifted Education International*, 34 (1), 36–46, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261429416649047>.
29. Didachou, A., & Zafiri, M., "Assessing the Reading and Writing Skills of AI Learners through the Application of Differentiated Instruction and the Use of Portfolios: A Case Study. *American Journal of Education and Learning*, 5(2), 159–174, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.20448/804.5.2.159.174>.

30. Gibbs, K., "Voices in practice: challenges to implementing differentiated instruction by teachers and school leaders in an Australian mainstream secondary school", *Australian Educational Researcher*, 50(4), 1217–1232, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-022-00551-2>.
31. Juanjuan Ouyang, N. Y., "Differentiated Instruction: Meeting the Needs of All Learners", *Curriculum and Teaching Methodology*, 6(11), 2023, <https://doi.org/10.23977/curtm.2023.061111>.
32. Tomlinson, C. A., *How to differentiate instruction in mixed-ability classrooms*, Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development, 2001.
33. Langelaan, B. N., Gaikhorst, L., Smets, W., & Oostdam, R. J., "Differentiating instruction: Understanding the key elements for successful teacher preparation and development", In *Teaching and Teacher Education* (Vol. 140), 2024, Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2023.104464>.
34. Mohamed, F. T., Olamo, T. G., & Yemiru, M. A., "Effect of differentiated instruction on primary EFL students' writing performance and perception: The case of grade 7 students in Hawassa city, Ethiopia", *Social Sciences and Humanities Open*, 11, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2024.101230>.
35. Palieraki, S., & Koutrouba, K., "Differentiated instruction in information and communications technology teaching and effective learning in primary education", *European Journal of Educational Research*, 10(3), 1487–1504, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.12973/EU-JER.10.3.1487>
36. Ping Liu, "Applying Differentiated Instruction in Elementary Classrooms: Practice and Reflection of Student Teachers", *Journal of Education and Practice*, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.7176/jep/12-27-01>.
37. Shareefa, M, "Demystifying the Impact of Teachers' Qualification and Experience on Implementation of Differentiated Instruction", *International Journal of Education*, 16(1), 393–416, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2023.16122a>.
38. Shareefa, M., & Moosa, V, "The Most-cited Educational Research Publications on Differentiated Instruction: A bibliometric analysis", *European Journal of Educational Research*, 9(1), 331–349, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.9.1.331>.
39. Vijayan, S. S. G., & Mohamad Nasri, N, "Implementation of Learning and Facilitation of Differentiated Learning Approach for Primary School", *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 11(3), 2022, <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarped/v11-i3/14370>.
40. Yavuz, A. C., "The effects of differentiated instruction on turkish students' l2 achievement, and student and teacher perceptions", *Eurasian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 6(2), 313–335, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.32601/ejal.776002>

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